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An in vivo investigation of
dantrolene as potential antidote for
2,4-dinitrophenol toxicity

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DECLARATION

I certify that this work is original in its entirety and has not been submitted previously for any form of assessment.

The practical work was a collaboration effort. Yusuf Hussein and I performed the dantrolene exposure tests. Caitlin Bellamy, Jonah Moxey, Yusuf Hussein, Rewash Ale and myself took the samples from the subjects with the help of Dr Aidan Seeley, Dr Nia Davies and Professor Lisa Wallace. Data analysis and presentation and written work presented are all my work unless otherwise stated.

Signed *Beatriz Banka*

ABSTRACT

2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP) is widely used as a weight loss pill despite its severe and often lethal side effects. However, it has been labelled as not fit for human consumption, there is an increasing tendency in DNP toxicity related reports due to its intentional ingestion. DNP increases the basal metabolic rate and results in ATP depletion and excess heat production. DNP has a very small therapeutic index; therefore, it is extremely easy to overdose and currently, there is a lack of clinical guidelines or specific antidote. Dantrolene has been used as a muscle relaxant and as a treatment option for malignant hyperthermia. Dantrolene is a basic injectable drug, which could form a complex with the acidic DNP, therefore reduce its toxic effects. Dantrolene has been used successfully to treat DNP caused hyperthermia. *Lumbriculus variegatus* is a small freshwater oligochaete, which is an invertebrate, therefore not covered by The Animal (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986, and thus can provide an in vivo model for sublethal toxicology testing. In open underwater spaces, the touching of the head elicits a reversal in body position, while touching the tail elicits helical swimming. These locomotor behaviours are stereotyped behaviours that are amendable to quantification. The worms' motility without stimulation is measurable with the free locomotion assay. DNP significantly decreased the ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete both stereotypical behaviours, the body reversal and helical swimming movements and caused lethargy which resulted in a reduction in the area covered by their free locomotion. Dantrolene did not affect the worms significantly, *Lumbriculus variegatus* could fully recover in most cases when they were expressed to 1.25 μM dantrolene after DNP exposure. Dantrolene has the potential to reverse DNP caused toxicity, however, its efficiency is dependent on the concentration of DNP.

Keywords: 2,4-dinitrophenol, dantrolene, *Lumbriculus variegatus*, toxicity, antidote

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ABBREVIATIONS

DNP	2,4-dinitrophenol
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
ADP	Adenosine diphosphate
RYR1	ryanodine receptor isoform 1
mM	Millimolar
μM	micromolar
n	Number of replicates
ddH ₂ O	Double-distilled water
KCl	Potassium chloride
Ca(NO ₃) · 4H ₂ O	Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate
MgSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	Magnesium sulphate heptahydrate
HEPES	N-(2-Hydroxyethyl) piperazine-N'-(2-ethanesulfonic acid)
NaCl	Sodium chloride
Ca ²⁺	Calcium ion
pKa	Acid dissociation constant

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. 2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP)

1.1.1. History of DNP

2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP) is a yellow crystalline powder which has been used in the manufacture of munitions during the First World War by the French (Cutting, Mehrtens, & Tainter, 1933; Perkins, 1919) and since then as a wood preserver, herbicide, photographic developer and dye (Grundlingh, 2011). In 1933, Maurice Tainter at Stanford University discovered the significant weight loss caused by human consumption of DNP (Tainter, Stockton, & Cutting, 1933) and it led to the popularisation of DNP as a weight loss drug and was available without a prescription, in over-the-counter medications (Grundlingh, 2011). The use of DNP was encouraged following reports of its safe and rapid weight loss effects (Tainter, Stockton, & Cutting, 1933; Cutting, Mehrtens, & Tainter, 1933). Regular intake of DNP caused up to 1.5 kg weight loss per week by burning more fat and carbohydrates- reportedly “without any reported significant side effects” (Tainter, Cuttling, & Hines, 1935). However, individual responses significantly altered, DNP caused an average metabolic rate increase of 11% for every 100 mg ingested (Tainter, 1935; Dunlop, 1934; Harper, Dickinson, & Brand, 2001). As a response to reported side effects of DNP, such as cataracts, it has been labelled as ‘extremely dangerous and not fit for human consumption’ by the Federal Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act of 1938 (Colman, 2007; Agency for Toxic Substances & Disease Registry, 1995).

After 1938, medical prescription of DNP has stopped, although it has been prescribed during World War II to the Russian soldiers to keep them warm (Kurt, Anderson, & Petty, 1986).

In 1981, Dr Bachynsky introduced ‘intracellular hyperthermia therapy’ at his private weight loss clinic and started to prescribe ‘Mitcal’ to his patients - a drug which contained industrial DNP and processed by himself (Kurt, Anderson, & Petty, 1986). By late 1982, over 14,000 people were treated by ‘Mitcal’ and they started to report adverse effects such as sweating, shortness of breath and fever to the US Food and Drugs Administration (Grundlingh, 2011). Furthermore, a fatal case has been reported caused by an intentional overdose of ‘Mitcal’, in 1984 (Grundlingh, 2011). After

further investigation, Dr Bachynsky was convicted in 1986 of drug violation and was fined and prohibited from further dispensing of DNP to any patients. However, he continued to promote DNP for different 'medical claims' and worked together with Helvetia Pharmaceuticals that was developing DNP being used as cancer treatment known as intracellular hyperthermia therapy (Miami FBI, 2008).

1.1.2. The role of the Internet in the increased popularity of DNP

Regardless of the warning issued by the UK Food Standard Agency in 2003, which has labelled DNP as 'not fit for human consumption', DNP poisoning due to intentional indigestion is still an existing problem. Despite it is illegal to sell DNP for human consumption, it is still available to purchase in capsule formats, and many websites and forums even offer guidance for taking DNP as a weight-loss drug.

Petróczi et al. in 2015, found that DNP users are confident about managing the potential adverse effects of DNP, satisfied with the effects of DNP and consider DNP usage as a sign of being committed to bodybuilding. Furthermore, not the drug, but users are blamed for detrimental health conditions (Petróczi, et al., 2015).

1.1.3. Mechanism of action

DNP stimulates systemic oxygen consumption and at the same time decreases the formation of high-energy phosphate bonds in the mitochondria, known as uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation (Grundlingh, 2011). During the Krebs cycle CO₂ and H₂O, 2 ATP and 38 energy-rich phosphate bonds are produced. In this final phase of cellular respiration, ATP synthesises converts adenosine diphosphate (ADP) to ATP with an additional inorganic phosphate molecule.

DNP prevents the uptake of inorganic phosphate molecules into the mitochondria (Rognstad & Katz, 1969; Issekatz, 1984), inhibits of all energy-requiring processes and induces extra-mitochondrial accumulation of inorganic phosphate molecules to occur (Simon, 1953). This results in decreased ATP production within the cells.

Furthermore, DNP also acts as a chemical ionophore as it stops the final energy conversion by exporting proton ions (H⁺) which are needed for ATP production across the mitochondrial membrane, thus increasing the basal leak of protons (Harper, Dickinson, & Brand, 2001). This shift in the proton electrochemical gradient leads to potential energy dissipating as heat instead of being converted to ATP, which results

in rapid consumption of calories (Wallace & Starkov, 2000; McFee, Caraccio, McGuigan, Reynolds, & Bellanger, 2004). Due to the heat production, failure in the thermoregulatory homeostasis occurs which leads to uncontrolled hyperthermia (Hoch & Hogan, 1973).

Figure 1. DNP decreases ATP production and acts as a chemical ionophore, which leads to uncoupled oxidative phosphorylation and thus excess heat production.

1.1.3. Clinical features and toxicity of DNP

DNP has a very small therapeutic index; therefore, it is very easy to overdose. The lowest published lethal human oral dose of DNP is 4.3 mg/kg (Pace & Pace, 2002) and the highest reported dose taken and led to acute overdose but associated to survival and no complications is 2.4 g (Geiger, 1935).

Regardless of the warning in 2003, issued by the UK Food Standard Agency, which has labelled DNP as ‘not fit for human consumption’, DNP remained widely available to purchase and therefore, used by bodybuilders and those, who are wishing to lose a considerable amount of weight rapidly. A study in 2013 reports that 21.3% of those who took part in the survey has used DNP in the past 12 months alone or in addition to other performance enhancer drugs (Chandler & McVeigh, 2014), which can make DNP consumption more dangerous due to the lack of data of its contraindications.

Between 2007 and March 2019, 26 deaths have been reported to the National Poisons Information Service, and 18 from these 26 deaths occurred since January 2015, in the

United Kingdom (National Poison Information Service, 2018). The graph below shreds of evidence how the popularity of DNP increased since 2011.

Figure 2 Quarterly numbers of NPIS cases referred by telephone and TOXBASE accesses relating to systemic DNP exposure, January 2011 - March 2019 (National Poison Information Service, 2018)

Recently, Dufayet *et al.* on the 3rd of March 2020 presented a case about a 17 years old male bodybuilder who has been found dead in his home after ingested DNP (Dufayet, et al., 2020)

Currently, there are no specific antidote or clinical guidelines to treat DNP toxicity other than using a cold bath or ice packs to lower body temperature (Plater & Harrison, 2019). Also, the guidelines available for users on the internet is dissatisfactory as well. In addition, DNP is not classified as a recreational drug. Hence new drug development is expensive, and DNP causes a relatively low number of deaths compared to other substances, it is unlikely to pharmaceutical companies will invest in an antidote for DNP. Therefore, an existing drug, which has the potential to manage DNP caused toxicity should be recognised and applied to a lower overdose caused fatalities.

1.2. Dantrolene

Dantrolene was originally synthesised by Snyder and his team in 1967 (Snyder, Davis, Bickerton, & Halliday, 1967). Due to its chemical, dantrolene is highly lipophilic, therefore poorly soluble in water and it caused problems in clinical settings until the 1980s (Krause, Gerbershagen, Fiege, WeiBhorn, & Wappler, 2004). In animal studies, dantrolene found to have muscle relaxant properties due to depressing the excitation-contracting coupling and therefore enabling skeletal muscles to transform a chemical signal at the neuromuscular junction into a muscle contraction (Snyder, Davis, Bickerton, & Halliday, 1967; Ellis & Bryant, 1972). In 1975, an *in vivo* study in Landrace pigs found dantrolene efficient to treat and prevent malignant hyperthermia (Harrison, 1975).

Figure 3. Chemical structure of dantrolene (PubChem)

1.2.1. Mechanism of action

In the skeletal muscle contraction, the contraction of actin and myosin fibres is required, which is activated by calcium ions (Krause, Gerbershagen, Fiege, WeiBhorn, & Wappler, 2004). For relaxation, the concentration of the myoplasm has to be below the mechanical threshold, which is achieved by transferring back calcium ions to the sarcoplasmic reticulum, which process is rapidly consuming ATP (Krause, Gerbershagen, Fiege, WeiBhorn, & Wappler, 2004). The ryanodine receptor isoform 1 (RYR1) and the alpha-1 subunit are the main calcium-releasing channel of the

sarcoplasmic reticulum, as the opening of RYR1 induces the efflux of calcium ions into myoplasm (Protasi, 2002; Shoshan-Barmatz & RH, 1998).

Susceptibility to malignant hyperthermia is associated with a prolonged opening state of the RYR1 in the sarcoplasmic reticulum which causes abnormal calcium metabolism within the skeletal muscle fibre (Krause, Gerbershagen, Fiege, WeiBhorn, & Wappler, 2004). The enhanced efflux of calcium ions from the sarcoplasmic reticulum into the myoplasm leads to longer and more intensive contraction of actin and myosin, which leads to hypercapnia, hyperthermia and acidosis (Krause, Gerbershagen, Fiege, WeiBhorn, & Wappler, 2004).

Dantrolene, a muscle relaxant, is able to dramatically decrease intracellular Ca^{2+} levels by binding to RYR1 and thereby suppressing the ability of the channel to open (Parness, 2005) and thus able to efficiently treat malignant hyperthermia.

Figure 4 Dantrolene is binding to ryanodine receptor isoform 1, therefore inhibits its calcium release from the sarcoplasmic reticulum into myoplasm. Reduced Ca^{2+} concentration in the myoplasm results in decreased heat, CO_2 and lactate production, muscle relaxation.

1.2.2. The role of dantrolene in DNP poisoning

DNP is known as an uncoupler of oxidative phosphorylation that clinically results in hyperthermia, tachycardia, metabolic acidosis and tachypnoea. Dantrolene is traditionally used to treat malignant hyperthermia, as it interferes with calcium release in skeletal muscle, therefore can prevent and treat abnormal calcium metabolism

caused hyperthermia. DNP overdose is often fatal as it is lack of specific reversal therapy, but dantrolene seems to be promising to address this problem.

Hence DNP is quite acidic with a pKa of 4.0 (Pearce & Simkins, 1968), a drug with basic properties would be able to form an acid-base complex with DNP by supramolecular complexation (acid + base = salt), which would lead to a decrease in the presence of the 'active' DNP. (Plater & Harrison, 2019). DNP found to be deprotonated to 2,4-dinitrophenolate in the blood (Plater & Harrison, 2019). Dantrolene has basic (pKa of 8.23) properties and injectable in a protonated form, therefore could form complexes with DNP anions in the blood and thus reduce its availability and hence toxic effects in the body (Plater & Harrison, 2019).

Kopec *et al* in 2019, presented two cases of DNP toxicity that were treated with dantrolene, as it is widely used in malignant hyperthermia treatment therefore it could treat DNP induced hyperthermia. In both cases, a young male patient presented to the emergency department after taking tablets containing DNP and showing symptoms of DNP toxicity such as tachycardia and elevated body temperature (Kopec, Kim, Mowry, Aks, & Kao, 2019). Both of them required intubation and received intravenous dantrolene treatment. In the first case, the patient's hyperthermia resolved, and he was discharged to home on the sixth hospital day. In the second case, despite dantrolene was able to resolve the patient's hyperthermia, the patient died approximately 4 hours after hospital arrival. However, the dosage of DNP is not clarified in this study, in Case 1 the patient took a double dose of his bodybuilding supplements, which included DNP, while in Case 2 the patient had a history of depression and ingested 8 tablets of DNP, therefore it suggests that, the efficacy of dantrolene treatment in DNP caused toxicity is highly dependent on the dose of DNP. As such, there is an unmet clinical need in determining suitable DNP antidote therapy. Further *in vivo* study is required to determine the underlying mechanisms of reversing DNP toxicity to reduce unnecessary morbidity and mortality associated with DNP exposure.

1.3. *Lumbriculus variegatus*

Lumbriculus variegatus is also known as blackworm or California blackworm and in the wild, lives in the shallows of freshwater ponds, marshes and lakes. The blackworm is widely distributed in Europe and North America, and also has been introduced into Australia, New Zealand and Africa (Brinkhurts & Jamieson, 1971). Aquatic oligochaetes, such as *Lumbriculus variegatus*, have an important role in freshwater aquatic communities, as they are aiding in the decomposition of organic materials in the sediment and serving as food for animals at higher trophic levels. An adult is formed of 150 to 250 body segments, and each segment has the ability to regenerate into a new worm when removed from the rest of the animal. This is the primary mechanism of reproduction.

In the natural habitat of *Lumbriculus variegatus*, they normally position themselves as their head is buried in the substrate and their tail is extended into the water column. This position allows them to obtain their nourishment from the organic material and microorganisms within the bottom sediments, however, the position of the tail makes them vulnerable to predation. In order to protect the tail, *Lumbriculus variegatus* has developed rapid withdrawal behaviours that are elicited by tactile stimulation or shadow (Drewes & Fournier, 1989; Zoran & Drewes, 1987). The neuronal circuits mediating rapid withdrawal responses in the blackworm are similar to those in other aquatic and terrestrial oligochaetes (Drewes, 1984; Zoran & Drewes, 1987).

Lumbriculus variegatus also has several context-specific locomotor 'escape' behaviours which are not mediated by the giant fibers (O'Gara, Bohannon, Teague, & Smeaton, 2004). In open underwater spaces, the touching of the head elicits a reversal in body position, while touching the tail elicits helical swimming (Drewes, 1999). Helical swimming consists of a series of helical waves that progress from the anterior end to the posterior end and alternate between clockwise and anticlockwise. These locomotor behaviours are stereotyped behaviours that are amenable to quantification, thus can be used for sublethal toxicology testing.

As an invertebrate, *L. variegatus* is not covered by The Animal (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 and thus under less regulatory constraint than conventional models.

Figure 5 *Lumbricus variegatus* (Storey, 2011)

1.4. Aim of this study

This investigation seeks to

- a) determine the sublethal effects of DNP, if there are any
- b) determine the sublethal effects of dantrolene, if there are any
- c) determine whether dantrolene can prevent the toxic effects of DNP
- c) determine whether dantrolene can reverse the effects of DNP

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Culturing *Lumbriculus variegatus*

2.1.1. Artificial pond water

Lumbriculus variegatus were derived from ALFA Fish Foods and have been cultured for at least six months before this study has started. Worms have been cultured in a tank containing artificial pond water.

For 1 litre of 100x artificial pond water, these were combined in 1 litre of ddH₂O:

- 1.3 mM KCl (0.095 g = 95 mg)
- 400 µM Ca(NO₃) · 4H₂O (0.095 g = 95 mg)
- 1.7 mM MgSO₄ · 7H₂O (0.42 g = 420 mg)
- 7.1 mM, HEPES (1.7 g)
- 100 mM NaCl (5.8 g)

Lumbriculus variegatus were fed with spirulina solution (10 mg per litre of artificial pond water), and UV-treated commercial fish food.

For each experiment, worms were randomly chosen 24 hours prior to use, and they were totally clear of any obvious morphological defects.

2.2. Preparation of drug treatments

2.2.1. DNP

A 10 mM stock solution of DNP was made by dissolving DNP in DMSO. The stock solution was stable at 4°C for 30 days. The stock solution was then diluted to required concentrations using DMSO on day of use.

2.2.2. Dantrolene

A 10 mM stock solution of dantrolene was made by dissolving dantrolene sodium salt in DMSO. The stock solution was made freshly (as its stability couldn't be maintained) and then diluted to required concentrations using DMSO on day of use.

2.3. Stereotypical Movement Assay

Worms have been plated out in 6-well plates the day before use. The artificial pond water was removed from the plates; worms have been washed with fresh artificial pond water and thereafter, 4 ml of fresh artificial pond water has been added to each well. To induce body reversal movement and helical swimming movement, the anterior end and posterior end of the worm were stimulated alternatively, five times, 10 seconds apart using a pipette tip. Movements were scored and recorded as **1 = No movement, 2 = Some Movement, 3 = Full Stereotypical Movement**

Artificial pond water then has been removed from the wells and each *Lumbriculus variegatus* has been exposed to different concentrations of drug solutions for 10 minutes:

- a) 0-50 μ M DNP solution
- b) 0-5 μ M dantrolene solution
- c) 0-50 μ M DNP solution for 10 minutes and then 1.25 μ M dantrolene solution

10 minutes after the drug exposure, stimulation by touching the anterior and posterior ends of *Lumbriculus variegatus* has been repeated, five times each end and using the same, 10 seconds interval between stimulations. Movements were scored and recorded.

Afterwards, drug solutions have been removed from the wells and washed with artificial pond water to remove remaining drug solutions. The artificial pond water was removed and fresh pondwater added to the well. Worms were then allowed to recover for 10 minutes. After 10 minutes, the worms were retested, and movements scored and recorded. After 24 hours worms were tested again to examine any long-term toxicity.

Afterwards, all *Lumbriculus variegatus* were treated with 70% ethanol, placed in virkon overnight and disposed. For statistical analysis data were expressed as a ratio of movement score after drug exposure relative to movement score prior exposure.

2.4. Free Locomotion Assay

Worms have been plated out in 6-well plates the day before use. The artificial pond water was removed from the plates; worms have been washed with fresh artificial pond water and thereafter, 2 ml (to limit vertical swimming) of fresh artificial pond water has been added to each well. 50 images have been taken 0.5 seconds apart.

Artificial pond water has been removed from the wells and each *Lumbriculus variegatus* has been exposed to different concentrations of drug solutions for 10 minutes:

- a) 0-50 μM DNP solution
- b) 0-5 μM dantrolene solution
- c) 0-50 μM DNP solution for 10 minutes and then 1.25 μM dantrolene solution

Afterwards, drug solutions have been removed from the wells and washed with artificial pond water to remove remaining drug solutions. The artificial pond water was removed and fresh pondwater added to the well. Worms were then allowed to recover for 10 minutes. After 10 minutes, pictures were retaken. After 24 hours pictures were taken again to examine any long-term toxicity.

Afterwards, all *Lumbriculus variegatus* were treated with 70% ethanol, placed in virkon overnight and disposed.

After images were collected, Z stack has been formed, then threshold has been set to detect worms and area covered by worms has been calculated (using ImageJ). Data were then normalised to the pre-exposure area covered and statistical analysis has

been conducted using GraphPad – PRISM8.

Figure 6 Images have been collected; Z stacks have been formed to calculate the area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus*

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was performed on data normalised to baseline data (using Microsoft Excel), and on the averaged intensities of the replicate measures. Data from each group were compared using Wilcoxon matched pairs signed rank tests, two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Dunnett’s multiple comparisons tests (using Graphpad- PRISM 8). All parametric data were expressed as means \pm standard errors of the mean (SEM). Data were considered significant if $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1. DNP

3.1.1. Stereotypical Movement Assay

Figure 7 The ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete (A) body reversal (B) helical swimming movements during DNP (0-50 µM) exposure, compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for eight independent (n=8) experiments with five replicates per experiment. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p < 0.05$ and ** if $p < 0.01$.

Figure 8 The ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete (A) body reversal (B) helical swimming movements 10 minutes and 24 hours after removal of DNP (0-50 µM), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Dunnett's multiple comparison test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for eight independent (n=8) experiments with five replicates per experiment. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p < 0.05$ and ** if $p < 0.01$.

Following 10 minutes exposure to DNP, statistical significance was found at doses 5, 12.5, 25 and 50 μM . As shown on Figure 7 A and B, there was a significant reduction in body reversal ($p=0.0156$, $p=0.0078$, $p=0.0078$ and 0.0078 , respectively) and in helical swimming ($p=0.0156$, $p=0.0078$, 0.0078 and $p=0.0078$, respectively) movements. Following the 10 minutes recovery period, *Lumbriculus variegatus* displayed significant decreases at doses 5, 12.5, 25 and 50 μM in body reversal movements ($p=0.0139$, $p<0.001$, $p<0.001$ and $p<0.001$ and, respectively) and in helical swimming movements ($p=0.0499$, $p<0.001$, $p<0.001$ and $p<0.001$, respectively) as shown on Figure 8 A and B. Significant reduction were found at doses 25 and 50 μM in the ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete both body reversal ($p=0.0078$ and $p<0.001$, respectively) and helical swimming ($p=0.0062$ and $p<0.001$, respectively) movements, as it is shown on Figure 8 A and B.

3.1.2. Free Locomotion Assay

Figure 9. The area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* during free locomotion movements, during DNP (0-50 µM) exposure (A), and the area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* 10 minutes and 24 hours after removal of DNP (0-50 µM) (B), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test Dunnett's multiple comparison has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean ± SEM values for five independent experiments with fifty images analysed per data point. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p < 0.05$, ** if $p < 0.01$ and *** if $p < 0.0001$.

Following 10 minutes exposure, 25 and 50 μM DNP significantly decreased the area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* ($p=0.0004$ and $p<0.0001$, respectively), as shown on Figure 9 A. As shown on Figure 9 B, further statistical significance was found at doses 25 and 50 μM after the 10 minutes recovery period ($p=0.0226$ and $p=0.0185$, respectively), but no significant reduction was found 24 hours after the removal of DNP in the area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus*.

3.2. Dantrolene

3.2.1. Stereotypical Movement Assay

Figure 10 The ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete (A) body reversal (B) helical swimming movements during dantrolene exposure (0-5 μM), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for seven independent ($n=7$) experiments with five replicates per experiment. Data is marked with * where it has been found statistically significant ($p<0.05$).

Figure 11 The ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete (A) body reversal (B) helical swimming movements 10 minutes and 24 hours after removal of dantrolene (0-5 µM), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Dunnett's multiple comparison test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for seven independent ($n=7$) experiments with five replicates per experiment. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p<0.05$ and ** if $p<0.01$.

3.2.2. Free Locomotion Assay

Figure 12. The area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* during free locomotion movements, during dantrolene (0-5 μM) exposure (A), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for five independent experiments with fifty images analysed per data point.

Figure 13 The area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* during free locomotion movements, 10 minutes (A) and 24 hours (B) after removal of dantrolene (0-50 μM) (B), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test and Dunnett's multiple comparison test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for five independent experiments with fifty images analysed per data point.

As shown on Figure 10 A, following 10 minutes exposure, at dose 5 μM dantrolene significantly decreased body reversal movement ($p=0.0312$) but no significant decrease was found in the ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete helical

swimming movements. Following 10 minutes recovery period, 5 uM dantrolene, as shown in Figure 11 A, *Lumbriculus variegatus* displayed a significant decrease in body reversal movement ($p=0.0069$). As shown in Figure 11 A, 10 minutes after removal of dantrolene, there was a significant reduction in helical swimming at doses 2.5 and 5 uM ($p=0.0033$ and $p=0.09$, respectively). Following 24 hours of drug removal, *Lumbriculus variegatus* displayed a significant decrease in helical swimming movement at doses 2.5 and 5 uM ($p=0.0033$ and $p=0.0053$, respectively), as shown in Figure 11 B. No statistically significant differences were found in the free locomotion movements of the worms, regardless of the doses, as shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

3.3. DNP exposure with dantrolene treatment

3.3.1. Stereotypical Movement Assay

Figure 14. The ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete (A) body reversal (B) helical swimming movements during DNP (0-50 μM) exposure with 1.25 μM dantrolene treatment, compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean ± SEM values for seven independent (n=7) experiments with five replicates per experiment. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p < 0.05$, ** if $p < 0.01$ and *** if $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 15 The ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete (A) body reversal (B) helical swimming movements 10 minutes and 24 hours after removal of DNP (0-50 µM) and dantrolene (1.25 µM), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Dunnett's multiple comparison test has been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for seven independent (n=7) experiments with five replicates per experiment. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p < 0.05$, ** if $p < 0.01$ and *** if $p < 0.0001$.

As shown in Figure 14 A and B, there was a significant reduction at doses 5, 12.5, 25 and 50 µM DNP in the ability of *Lumbriculus variegatus* to complete body reversal ($p=0.0156$, $p=0.0156$, $p=0.0156$ and $p=0.0156$, respectively) and helical swimming

movements ($p=0.0156$, $p=0.0156$, $p=0.0156$ and $p=0.0156$, respectively). Following the 10 minutes recovery period, *Lumbriculus variegatus* displayed significant decreases at doses 5, 12.5, 25 and 50 μM DNP in body reversal ($p<0.0001$, $p<0.0001$, $p<0.0001$ and $p<0.0001$, respectively), and in helical swimming movements ($p<0.0001$, $p<0.0001$, $p<0.0001$ and $p<0.0001$, respectively), as shown in Figure 15 A and B. Following the 24 hours recovery period, as shown in Figure 15 A and B, there was a significant reduction in body reversal and helical swimming movements at dose 50 μM DNP ($p<0.0001$ and $p<0.0001$, respectively).

3.3.2. Free Locomotion Assay

Figure 16. The area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* during free locomotion movements, during DNP (0-50 μM) exposure and 1.25 μM dantrolene treatment (A), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. The area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* during free locomotion movements, 10 minutes and 24 hours after removal of DNP (0-50 μM) and 1.25 μM dantrolene (B), compared to baseline movements measured in artificial pond water incubation. Wilcoxon test and Dunnett's multiple comparison test have been used for analysis and data are shown as mean \pm SEM values for six independent experiments with fifty images analysed per data point. Data is marked where statistical significance has been found as * if $p < 0.05$, ** if $p < 0.01$ and *** if $p < 0.0001$.

Following 10 minutes exposure to DNP at a concentration of 50 μM , the area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* was found significantly decreased ($p=0.0049$) compared to pre-exposure, as shown in Figure 16 A. Statistical significance was also found after the 10 minutes recovery period at DNP dose 50 μM ($p=0.0276$), as shown in Figure 16 B.

4. DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Sublethal effects of drug exposure

4.1.1. DNP

The stereotypical movement and free locomotion assays have shown that *Lumbriculus variegatus* is valuable in vivo model for sublethal testing with DNP. Following DNP exposure, first, the worms became hyperactive with an observable writhing and coiling behaviour for a few minutes, then they became lethargic and hyporesponsive to tactile stimulation. In general, the onset of the writhing behaviour was related to the DNP concentration (those with higher dose showed the reaction in the shortest time to exposure). As the results have shown, DNP above a concentration of 0.5 μM induced hyporesponsive behaviour which has adversely affected the worms' ability to complete body reversal and helical swimming movements (as shown in Figure 6 A and B, respectively), especially those who have been exposed to higher doses of DNP. Furthermore, the hyporesponsive behaviour and the lethargy were still observable even 10 minutes after removal of DNP, and full recovery of *Lumbriculus variegatus* was not observable even after 24 hours recovery period (as shown in Figure 6 C and D). Based on the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the data, the area covered by *Lumbriculus variegatus* during free locomotion has been significantly decreased after DNP exposure at higher doses (25 and 50 μM), (as shown in Figure 7 A) and the worms were not able to recover after 10 minutes (as shown in Figure 7 B). After the 24 hours recovery period, the worms started to show some recovery, however, they still couldn't show a full recovery (as shown in Figure 7 B).

Therefore, *Lumbriculus variegatus* is found to be sensitive to DNP and its toxic effects, and they did not have the ability to recover from the adverse effects of DNP, especially in higher doses, without additional therapies.

4.1.2. Dantrolene

The stereotypical movement and free locomotion assays have shown that dantrolene does not produce an adverse effect on *Lumbriculus variegatus*. Following dantrolene exposure, the worms did not show any hyperactivity or any changes in their responsiveness to tactile stimulation. Despite the DMSO buffer which has been used to improve the solubility of dantrolene, at higher concentrations (2.5 and 5 μM) dantrolene precipitated from the solution and this caused some reduction in the *Lumbriculus variegatus* responsiveness to tactile stimulation. This phenomenon became more observable by time, which resulted in a decreased ability of the worms to complete body reversal and helical swimming movements (as shown in Figure 7 C and D). Interestingly, the precipitation caused effects were not measurable during the free locomotion assay, while the presence of dantrolene seemed to improve their motility, however, these improvements did not find to be statistically significant (as shown in Figure 9). The reliability of the data would be impacted by the precipitation; thus, it has indicated the exclusion of these higher concentrations as a treatment option. For further tests to investigate the effect of dantrolene in DNP induced toxicity, the concentration of 1.25 μM dose has been used, which did not cause any significant effects on *Lumbriculus variegatus*.

To summarise and reflect on the data analysis, dantrolene found to be ineffective regarding causing any physiological or behavioural changes in *Lumbriculus variegatus*, thus it can be used as an antidote for further experiments.

4.2. The effect of dantrolene in DNP caused toxicity

First, each *Lumbriculus variegatus* has been exposed to different concentrations of DNP and its immediate effects (hyperactivity, writhing and coiling behaviour) seemed to be lack, indeed lethargic behaviour was present by the time of the 1.25 μM dantrolene treatment. 10 minutes after the dantrolene exposure, the worms remained hyporesponsive to tactile stimulation, which results in a significant decrease in their ability to complete body reversal and helical swimming movements (as shown in Figure 10 A and B). This hyporesponsive behaviour still presented even after 10 minutes of the drug removal (as shown in Figure 10 C and D). As results have shown,

after the 24 hours recovery period, the majority of the worms were able to match their stereotypical movement, completing ability to the pre-exposure levels, however, those, who were exposed to DNP at the concentration of 50 μM , remained hyporesponsive to tactile stimuli which resulted in a significant decrease in their ability to complete body reversal and helical swimming movements (as shown in Figure 10 C and D).

However, the worms remained hyporesponsive, the lethargic behaviour seemed to be resolved by dantrolene as soon as 10 minutes after its exposure, as the area covered due to the free locomotion of *Lumbriculus variegatus* showed a significant reduction only if the worm were previously exposed to DNP at the concentration of 50 μM . Based on statistical analysis, at lower concentrations, the worms' locomotion has matched the pre-exposure standard (as shown in Figure 11 A). Following the 10 minutes recovery period, the only significant decrease was measured at the concentration of 50 μM of DNP; the majority of *Lumbriculus variegatus* was able to recover in this short period. After the 24 hours recovery period, all the worms showed full recovery, as shown in Figure 11 B.

The study demonstrates a correlation between the presence of dantrolene and the recovery of *Lumbriculus variegatus* from DNP caused toxicity.

4.3. Limitations of this study

The generalisability of the results is limited by only one dose (1.25 μM) of dantrolene has been investigated and higher concentrations of dantrolene might act faster and potentially could lead to a full recovery in higher concentrations of DNP as well. In addition, *Lumbriculus variegatus* has been exposed to dantrolene only 10 minutes after DNP exposure, therefore further studies required to investigate whether the dose of dantrolene has to be increased gradually by the time has passed since DNP exposure. This research clearly illustrates the ability of dantrolene to reverse the toxic effects caused by 10 minutes DNP exposure, but also raises the question of its ability to reverse the effects of DNP after repeated or longer periods of exposure.

4.4. Conclusions

This research aimed to determine whether DNP and dantrolene produce sublethal effects on *Lumbriculus variegatus* and if dantrolene has the potential to prevent or reverse the toxic effects of DNP. The data suggest that dantrolene has no significant effects on *Lumbriculus variegatus* therefore in line with the hypothesis, it could be used as an antidote for DNP exposure caused toxicity. Based on the quantitative and qualitative analyses of the behaviour of *Lumbriculus variegatus*, it can be concluded that *Lumbriculus variegatus* is sensitive to DNP exposure dose-dependently as they have shown worsening adverse effects after being exposed to higher concentrations. The results indicate that DNP causes hyporesponsiveness and lethargy in *Lumbriculus variegatus*, and they have a limited ability to spontaneously recover from these conditions. In addition, if some recovery has occurred, spontaneously or as a result of dantrolene treatment, it more likely affected the lethargy rather than the hyporesponsive state. This research clearly illustrates the ability of dantrolene to reverse the toxic effects caused by DNP, but it also raises a question about the effectiveness of dantrolene after exposure to higher doses of DNP. These results corroborate the case study presented by Kopec et al, in 2019, in which a patient has died, and another has successfully recovered from DNP overdose following dantrolene treatment. Future studies are needed to determine whether dantrolene is effective with a delay in its administration and after longer or repeated exposure to DNP.

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Appendix 1

Material	Manufacturer
NaCl	Melford
KCl	Melford
Ca(NO₃) · 4H₂O	Duchefa
Mg(SO₄) · 7H₂O	Duchefa
HEPES	Melford
DNP	Sigma-Aldrich
Dantrolene	Sigma
DMSO	Sigma